

ISSN 2348 – 8417

शास्त्रमञ्जूषा

The Śāstramañjūṣā

<https://sites.google.com/site/praachiprajnaa/sastramanjusa>

(A Virtual Publication for the Peer Reviewed Research Papers on Indology)

Of

प्राची प्रज्ञा

Prachi Prajna

<https://sites.google.com/site/praachiprajnaa>

Indexed in DOAJ

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17th Issue / Vol. IX – December, 2023

शास्त्रमञ्जूषा / The śāstramañjūṣā

<https://sites.google.com/site/prachiprajnaa/sastramanjusa>, a Virtual Publication for the Peer Reviewed Research papers on Indology of प्राची प्रज्ञा / Prachi Prajna (ISSN 2348 – 8417) <https://sites.google.com/site/prachiprajnaa>

17th Issue / Vol. IX – 31st December, 2023

Scope:

The śāstramañjūṣā is a Virtual Publication for the Peer Reviewed Research papers on Indology, conglomerated to any branch of Sanskrit Studies, i.e. Vedas, Vedāṅgas, Upaniṣads, Philosophies, Purāṇas, Smṛtis, Literature, Poetics, Grammar, Tantras, Astrology, Astronomy and Modern subjects like Computational Linguistics, Environmental Science and allied fields. It aims, without sacrifice of scholarly standards, to engage readers throughout the globe. The Publication remains committed to the re-appraisal of accepted views, and scholarship should reinforce the committed spirit of indology encompassed in the Classical and the oldest language Sanskrit.

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सम्पादकीयम्

सहस्रेभ्यो वर्षेभ्यः पूर्वं मानवेन लेखनकलाया आविष्कारः कृतः । तदारभ्यैयावल्लिखिता सामग्री विभिन्नरूपेण लभ्यते । इयं लेखनप्रक्रिया ईष्टकेषु, पाषाणेषु, चर्मसु, वस्त्रेषु, भुर्जपत्रेषु, ताम्रपट्टेषु, तालपत्रेषु, कर्गजेषु, अन्येषु धातुनिर्मितेषु पट्टेषु, कर्गजेषु च भवति स्म । एतेषु सर्वेषु लिखिता सामग्री पाण्डुलिपिविज्ञानेऽन्तर्भवति । 'पाण्डुलिपिः' इति शब्दः आङ्ग्लभाषया manuscript इत्युच्यते यस्यार्थो भवति हस्तलेखः । एवञ्च manuscript इति पदं हस्तलेखरूपं योगार्थं परिहृत्य व्यापकेष्वर्थेषु यथा अभिलेखेषु, शिलालेखेषु, ताम्रलेखेषु, स्मारकलेखेषु, आज्ञापत्रेषु, दानपत्रेषु तथा प्रकाशनपूर्वेषु सर्वेषु लेखेषु व्यवहियते । The American People's Encyclopedia अनुसारं मुद्रणात् पूर्वं सर्वमपि साहित्यं पाण्डुलिपिरिति उच्यते, यत् कर्गजेषु अन्येषु केषुचिदपि वस्तुषु लिखितं, टङ्कितम्, उट्टङ्कितं, उत्कीर्णितं वा स्यात् । पाण्डुलिपिविज्ञानस्य अनेके पक्षाः सम्भवन्ति । तत्र प्रथमः पक्षः ग्रन्थरचनाविषयकः यत्र ग्रन्थविषय-तद्रचयितृ-तत्कालप्रभृतीनां विचाराः भवन्ति । द्वितीयः पक्षः लिपिविज्ञानम्, यत्र लिपि-लिपिकार-लिप्यासन-लिपीकरणसाधनानां विचाराः प्रवर्तन्ते । तृतीयः पक्षः भाषाविज्ञानं यत्र ग्रन्थप्रयुक्तभाषाविषये तत्प्रयुक्तव्याकरणादिविषये चर्चा भवति । "प्राची प्रज्ञा" इति पत्रिकायाः शास्त्रमञ्जूषाया अस्मिन्नङ्के एतान् त्रीन्नपि पक्षानवलम्ब्य कतिचिन्महत्त्वपूर्णानि शोधपत्राणि प्रस्तूयन्ते । आशासे एतानि शोधपत्राणि संस्कृतभाषानिबद्धपाण्डुलिपीनां संरक्षणे सम्पादने च सहायकानि भवेयुः ।

सुज्ञानकुमारमाहान्तिः

मुख्यसम्पादकः

शास्त्रमञ्जूषा / प्राचीप्रज्ञा

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Palm-leaf Manuscripts: their Preservation and Conservation in Oḍiṣā

Laxman Majhi

Abstract

The conservation of palm-leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā, a state in western India, is a critical endeavour to safeguard an invaluable cultural and historical heritage. Palm-leaf manuscripts, known as "Tālapatra Granthas" in the local language, are ancient textual records written on dried and processed palm leaves. These manuscripts contain valuable knowledge in the domains of religion, literature, science, and various other subjects. This research paper aims to explore the challenges faced in the conservation of palm-leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā and proposes effective strategies for their preservation. The study encompasses an in-depth examination of the factors contributing to the deterioration of palm-leaf manuscripts, including environmental conditions, biological threats, physical damage, and human interventions. Furthermore, the research investigates existing conservation practices and techniques employed in Oḍiṣā and evaluate their effectiveness. It explores traditional methods of manuscript preservation, such as the use of natural oils and herbal treatments, as well as modern conservation approaches, including digitization and non-invasive imaging technologies. The paper also delves into the significance of palm-leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā's cultural and historical context, emphasizing their role in preserving indigenous knowledge and intellectual traditions. It highlights the need for a comprehensive conservation plan that balances the preservation of the manuscripts' material integrity while ensuring wider accessibility for scholars, researchers, and the general public. Through a multidisciplinary approach, combining insights from conservation science, cultural heritage management, and archival studies, this research paper presents a framework for the sustainable conservation of palm-leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā. It proposes recommendations for improved storage conditions, handling procedures, and conservation treatments, considering the unique characteristics of these manuscripts and their cultural significance. Ultimately, the findings of this research contribute to the broader discourse on manuscript conservation, providing practical insights and guidelines for preserving and promoting the rich legacy of palm-leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā, thereby ensuring their transmission to future generations and fostering a deeper understanding of the region's cultural heritage.

Key Words: - Palm-leaf manuscripts, Conservation, Preservation, Tālapatra Granthas, Cultural heritage, Historical records, Physical damage, Traditional preservation methods, Digitization, Archival studies.

Historical Background of Palm-Leaf Manuscripts - Man in the past had chosen palm-leaf

as one of the materials for writing and keeping records. The use of palm-leaves was in vogue in almost all South and Southeast Asian Countries. Even though the use of the palm-leaves is very old, the use of palm-leaves came into practice sometime in 6th century B.C. The earliest availability of palm-leaf manuscripts in Nepal was from 7th century A.D. There are different forms and types

of manuscripts depending upon the support materials that contain the content; it may be Paper, palm-leaf, birch bark, bamboo- leaf, sanchipot, leather, textiles, clay tablets, etc. However out of these materials, it is the Palm-leaf Manuscripts which are frequently used in coastal parts of India; may be due to abundance of Palm trees in those regions and Oḍiṣā needs special mention as far as writing on palm-leaves are concerned and present data also proves the notion that it is Oḍiṣā which has taken prominent role in preserving our great hoary past in the form of Palm-leaf writings.

Ancient Traditions of palm-leaf writings in

Oḍiṣā - We don't have any knowledge regarding the exact place and period in history when palm-leaf manuscripts were started to have originated in Oḍiṣā.

The ancient tradition of writing on stone is seen in Dhauli and Udayagiri rock edicts but it speaks of nothing about writing on palm-leaf at that time. That doesn't mean that this practice was not prevalent at that time. However as far as evidence is concerned, from one of the copper plate inscriptions of Śailodbhava dynasty it is learnt that the script was first written on a palm-leaf and then transcribed on to the copper plate by the copying method as is noted by Dr. Satya Nārāyaṇa Rājguru in his book of origin of Oḍiā Script and it can be assumed that the art of palm-leaf writing was an established tradition in Oḍiṣā even in 6th or 7th Century A.D. However there is some sculptural evidence that proves the prevalence of palm-leaf writings from that of Paraśurāmeśvara, Mukteśvara in Bhubaneswar, Sun Temple at Koṅārka, Jagannātha Temple at Dharakote and in some of the Buddhist sculptures in Oḍiṣā, say 11th Century image of Buddha in Haripura near Khordhā road Railway Station etc. As palm-leaf is an organic origin therefore it couldn't be preserved for long; hence there was a strong tradition in Oḍiṣā to copy and rewrite the subject or content in fresh palm-leaves by kings, nobles, royal people as well as the commoners who can afford to it during leisurely period, say, in rainy season as being the agrarian society they do not have much work at their hand and the artisans who adept in writing on palm-leaves are engaged to propagate the concept of palm-leaf manuscripts in the state.

The earliest dated palm-leaf manuscript available in Oḍiṣā State Museum is that of Abhinavagītagovinda of 15th century AD. But this tradition has been there since 6th/7th Century AD as discussed above from the temple walls. By this method of copying the manuscripts the Mahābhārata of Sārālā Dās and Bhāgavata of Atibaḍi Jagannātha Dās spread in Oḍiṣā. During the Bhakti movement in 16th Century AD especially after Jagannātha Dās and arrival of Sri Caitanya Dev the palm-leaf writing tradition was an house-hold activity in almost each nook and corners and thus "Bhāgavata Ṭuṅgī" or Gādi Ghara came in a big way. Though there were temples to worship gods and goddesses still use to have this Gādi Ghara almost in every village which was

a form of Library with the religious scriptures for the then People of Oḍiṣā which not only worked as worshipping centre but also a form of literacy programme as every pious Oḍiā would enchant Bhagabat in the evening time after a hard labour in day time. Being agrarian economy people had to spend time in this community centre to take part in the religious discourse and even this was enchanted before a dying person with a strong belief that doing so would enable the person to attain salvation in the after-world.

All these Gādi Ghara or Bhāgavata Ṭuṅgīs would be supplied the palm-leaf manuscripts at regular interval as old ones are to be replaced with the new and fresh manuscripts. Some household and the Jamindārs also do the same practice out of their religious fervour and indirectly it was spreading Library Movement in those days while practicing religious duties as well as that of literacy movement indirectly. As a result numerous palm-leaf manuscripts are available even today.

The Etching tradition: a dying art in Oḍiṣā - The etching or painting on the seasoned palm-leaves is also an art as one has to be technically sound to incise the palm-leaf through an iron stylus. Now-a-days this tradition is almost extinct due to introduction of paper and printing press and naturally the rural folks who were adept in this writing have switched over their activity to other fields of profession and thus we have lost this tradition, the style of works, and their expertise is nowhere seen. It is said that the Oḍiā script was shaped so circularly due to writing on palm-leaf as the script was bound to change and takes a cursive shape on the palm-leaf due to its parallel venation where-in the vascular venation system of plant leaves are parallel to each other and nature provides an opportunity to sustain and maintain the writing style. Due to this nature of leaves, the scripts when written, the leafy materials are not subjected to tearing away of the same and the alphabets are incised with ease and comfort. Our scripts are like that of South Indian scripts due to this etching tradition on palm-leaf. As Oḍiṣā is historically and culturally linked to South India from the period of Khāravēla to medieval ages, it was quite natural that Oḍiā script was influenced by the South Indian cursive writings, and credit must go to the nature of support material, i.e., palm-leaf. Therefore palm-leaf manuscripts are not only our pride or identity but also the torch bearer of our socio-cultural ethos through the ages while upholding the thousands of years of art traditions through etching and incising on palm-leaves, which has now being turned out as a dying art, and should be preserved for posterity through various mechanisms, i.e., copying, digitizing, conserving and preserving through modern state of the art technology or indigenous practices.

Conservation: Definition and Nature - The word 'Conservation' means a practice that protects and enhances the cultural value of any art object. It is a process that varies from simple repair or maintenance to that of highly complicated nature. It emphasizes that of fumigation, documentation, digitization, restoration etc. that provides longevity to the manuscripts. Going by the

definition, it says that Conservation is any direct or indirect action on a damaged or undamaged manuscript aimed at enhancing the life of the manuscript.

There are two types of conservation based upon their methodology and nature as defined by National Mission for Manuscripts, i.e., Preventive and Curative conservation. The former is the indirect action and latter is the direct action which increases the life expectancy of the manuscripts. For example, the re-organization of storage, regular inspection, using indigenous practices for repelling insects and other microbes from manuscripts, ecology and maintenance of collection center or almirahs etc.-are all called preventive conservation, and similarly any action directly aimed at doing certain practices or techniques on the palm-leaves like fumigation, solvent cleaning, tissue lining etc. are called curative conservation.

In the field especially the mutts, temples, individual households etc the manuscripts are in bad state of conservation due to inadequate of funding and negligence at the hand of the keeper. It is also costly matters as one cannot get the staff engaged with the state-of-the art technology and thus they should approach certain methodology so that it will be preserved for the posterity and if required they may go for indigenous practices of conservation like applying Neem, Turmeric, black cumin, sweet flag, cloves, pepper, cinnamon, camphor etc. in different forms and mixture in certain techniques as a preventive measure so that the manuscripts are not allowed to deteriorate at comparably lesser expenses and it is not involved with so much of techniques and technology as seen in the modern day practices.

Current Practices of Scientific Conservation - We employ both preventive as well as curative practice of conservation as cited above, besides traditional methods for preserving the palm-leaf manuscripts not only in Oḍiṣā but all over India as a normal tested and tried procedure that may be briefed as under.

(a) Preventive Conservation - There is a saying that prevention is better than cure in medical parlance and the same is true in case of conservation science also. By definition, it is nothing but all sorts of indirect action aimed at increasing the longevity of the Mss. and preventive conservation of Palm-leaf Mss. was there since the ages in traditional manner in households of the villages of Oḍiṣā but in rudimentary form. The new age research and new technique did help a lot in augmenting this technique. Some precautionary measure with preventive conservation methodology may be discussed as follows.

1. Proper mechanism to maintain the Relative Humidity and Light in control in the holdings of the Mss.
2. Cross-Ventilation should be maintained in the repositories.
3. Mss. shouldn't be allowed to be placed one above the other.
4. It should be inspected through quarantine visit at regular intervals.
5. Handling of the Mss.: While taking a Mss. from the shelf one shouldn't take away the book holding it from top or head of the spine; but from its middle.
6. Manuscripts should be fumigated with fungicides and insecticides suitably for preventing the attack of insects and fungus.

7. Regular dusting and cleaning of the Mss. as well as the repositories be done by trained conservators.
8. Damp environment be avoided for books or Manuscripts.
9. Air Conditioner, if present, should be maintained thorough out the day and night without any interruption and this facility cannot be provided, then it should be avoided lest it would damage the Mss. more than that of the environs without Air Conditioner. As switching off the Air conditioner would cause a huge temperature gap causing more contraction and expansion of the folios of the Mss. which are organic in nature, hence causing more destruction of the organic materials like palm leaves. Rather a conducive atmosphere of Standard Temperature of 22-24 degree centigrade with Relative Humidity around 55% is maintained by certain mechanisms.
10. The traditional fungicides and herbicides could be used which are having no harmful impact upon art object as well as the internal environs.
11. Other preventive materials like naphthalene crystals or anything like these repellants are useful in the preventive conservation.
12. The Mss. shouldn't be piled up as a mound; rather placed in the racks such a manner so that it would seem to be displayed to the Keeper of the holdings from a distance and any insect or pest attack can be noticed easily without any effort and it would help a lot in maintaining the Mss.
13. The vacuum cleaner may be used in cleaning the floor or inside part of the Museum/Archives but not directly upon the folios/bundles of the Mss.
14. The binding of the folios of the Mss. should be neatly done in symmetrical and in tight manner so that the thread would exert equal pressure all along the surface of the strong cover board that helps protecting the bundles of the Mss. This binding of the Mss. by thread in the middle also a technique that shouldn't be of more thickness compared to that of the central hole of the bundle; rather, it should provide flexibility to the folios inside Mss.
15. Minimum use of chemicals is always desirable as an ethics of conservation and minimum interference gives maximum result.
16. Whatever chemicals/processes be used it should be reversible in nature and be documented properly so that the next course of action can be visualized by the restorers in the event of being further damaged by any agents.
17. If possible, the folios are treated with fungicidal papers if it is very much prone to the fungal spores due to moist and continued humidity.
18. The Mss. should be documented and digitalized properly so that it wouldn't be opened up by the research scholar's frequently as frequent handling of the same causes more damage as most of the time these Mss. might not be bound properly by the trained technicians. The laxity of the binding can be more disastrous for the Mss. as it would house the insects which affect the folios.
19. White painting containing Titanium-dioxide which has the capacity to absorb UV light may be used in the walls of storage or display rooms so as to have minimal impact upon the objects.

19. Even UV filters or special hard plastic filters of fluorescent tube lights are used in the storage.
20. Photo copying machines are placed at a safe distance for the Mss. as Ozone emitted through these machines may harm Mss.
21. Wooden storage, sometimes used, may have negative impact as it may give off acidic vapours, hence be given coats of emulsion paint on the surface of the wooden storage.
22. Camphor tablets, Dry Neem/Tobacco leaves are placed in the shelf.

All these precautionary measures along with preventive methods are useful for maintaining the safety and longevity of the Mss.

(b) Curative Conservation - As the name suggests, the curative conservation is a direct action aimed at increasing the longevity of the cultural property and it intervenes directly with the objects, say Mss. Some of the methods employed by the Art Restorers in Oḍiṣān repositories may be described as follows.

1. **Documentation:** It is of prime importance and should be done properly like photographic or textual or anything using modern techniques to keep a record of the same for both before and after the conservation to maintain the sanctity of the conservation.
2. **Fumigation:** Though a preventive mechanism, it is employed in the conservation process before going on for any curative measures using Para-di-chloro- benzene (PDCB) and Thymol as insecticides or fungicides respectively which would penetrate deep into the layers of folios and act as repellent.
3. **Stacking of Folios:** If folios of the Mss. are stacked with each other then, separation be done by skilful restorer using some suitable organic solvents like Ethanol and if possible, may be through syringes so that careful measure wouldn't damage the fragile Mss.
4. **Dry Cleaning:** As an ethics we should try to avoid the chemicals and if the folios are dusty or dirty and stained then initially dry cleaning with soft brushes be done to clean the individual folios smoothly from centre of the folios to the outwardly manner.
5. **Solvent Cleaning:** If the dry cleaning with brushes does not yield any good result then suitable solvent, say, diluted Ethyl Alcohol may be used to clean the surface of the folios with some insecticides. The dilution of the Alcohol depends upon the atmospheric humidity which fluctuates seasonally and diurnally due to close proximity with the sea coast, especially in coastal Oḍiṣā so that it would not dampen the leaves. So any volatile compound used should be checked first as volatility of organic compounds also differ case by case. Other organic compounds may be used are Carbon Tetrachloride, Toluene, Benzene, Petroleum Ether etc.
6. **Flexibility of Brittled Palm-leaves:** Most of the time we observe the hardening of the palm leaves due to loss of essential oil of the folios with the passage of time which makes the leaves brittle and fragile. So to regain the

flexibility in the dried leaves some of the chemicals like camphor oil, citronella oil, glycerine, lemon grass oil, clove oil etc. can be used in aqueous medium while combining alcohols in different proportions. This would impart not only flexibility but strength to the embrittled leaves.

7. **Tissue Filling:** This technique is applied when the upper epidermal layer of the Palm leaves are destroyed by the insects and the small insect holes appear on the surface as the pests make tunnel while deriving food from the organic substrates like palm leaves which is composed of carbohydrates like celluloses, hemicelluloses and fats, lignin, minerals, resins etc. So the loss of layers can be compensated by filling the holes with a pulp of tissue paper with Carboxyl Methyl Cellulose (CMC) added with an insecticide like Sodium Fluoride can be helpful which is very small in percentage, hence sodium salts will have least effect upon the folios.
8. **Reinforcement Technique:** Some times what happens that, the edges of the folios or even substantial parts of the palm leaves are lost either due to insect or fungal attack or due to stacking folios or improper storage. In that case in a bundle/ Mss some folios are there without any edges or parts there-of, which exerts unequal pressure upon the whole surface of the folios, hence the bundle as a whole causing other folios to bend and continual bending of folios for a prolonged period cause wear and tear of leaves and it loses its suppleness and becomes brittle. So, to eradicate this problem a restorer compensates the lost part of the folios by adjoining it with another fragmented piece of palm leaf with similar thickness, width, colour, texture, and length in such a way that the cultural aesthetics wouldn't be lost. This process is otherwise called as Integration of Folios and poly vinyl acetate can be used to glue the fragmented pieces with the help of a spatula and later on this treated folio would be subjected to mechanical pressure so that it wouldn't bend rather be straightened under, if possible, a transparent glass surface.
9. **Solvent Lamination:** Lamination treatment is given to the precious Mss. which are having deterioration to such an extent that it is irreparable in normal processes. In this case a method called Solvent Lamination is done with transparent tissue paper and cellulose acetate foil and medium of organic solvent like acetone which is applied with a cotton swab so that the weakened leaves would be strengthened. But one must make a solubility test before using acetone as insoluble writings will have no problem. This is very important in case of illustrated manuscripts.
10. **Re-inking the writing:** As palm leaves are of hundreds of years old and legibility is lost due to loss of carbon pigments, hence re-inking can be done to give the engravings into a readable form. In Oḍiṣā we have Tāla leaves which are basically engraved by stylus upon the surface of the leaves. Hence carbon black can be prepared by any lamp with oil fuel and this carbon black when rubbed with the incision with a soft cotton cloth with glue, the writings can be read properly with ease

and convenience. The excess of lamp black is removed with the soft cloth and may be, possibly, by ethanol so that the extraneous substances or colours will be wiped off the surface of the palm-leaves.

So, all these processes employed in Oḍiṣā in modern days may not be done at all circumstances. The curative conservation process is a dynamic action upon the art objects depending upon the nature and extent of the damage that is inflicted by natural or biological attack or even human apathy. So, these methods may or may not be used for all purposes, but it serves as a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) in restoring, conserving and preserving the palm leaf manuscripts in Oḍiṣā. Now-a-days more and more indigenous practices are being adopted by our researchers using neem, turmeric, camphor, sandal wood, etc. so that it will have minimal impact upon the manuscripts as well as in the laboratories. Hope, Conservators/researchers/art-restorers would find their due place in making innovative approach in preserving the palm-leaf manuscripts in coming days and leave their foot prints in making new dimension in the field of research in this sphere of activity there-by conserving the rich documentary legacy of the state aswell as India.

Furthermore, it is worthwhile to mention that as per the data available from National Mission for Manuscripts, under Ministry of Culture, Government of India, we have more than Two millions of Manuscripts all over India and Oḍiṣā boasts to have more than Five lakhs of them in the country which speaks a volume of our own distinct identity and pride and we should preserve this grand legacy for our posterior generation at any cost. This is the need of the hour and clarion call of our great forefathers.

Apathy in un-organized sectors like Bhāgavatatuṅgīs etc. - So the above scientific description of conservation of the palm-leaf gives an idea as to why these manuscripts are susceptible to damage and destruction in coastal part of India and so the state of Oḍiṣā. The Bhāgavatagādis, or the Tuṅgīs Mutts, Monasteries, Temples, Private Households or repositories in rural areas are not equipped with those technical personnel, techniques of preservation, and also the cost of the conservation may not inspire the owners of the repositories to do the conservation works. The high cost of the suitable chemicals as described above also adds to the woes of the custodians. Not only that, even there are sizeable number of custodians in our rural areas who are inimical to the conservation due their ignorance and they throw it into the ponds, rivers, lakes and some bury them in the burial grounds thinking that they are paying homage to these “Pothis” as a customary belief. Doing this practice, we not only dis-respect the manuscripts but also the content material within it and unfortunate thing is that these dying art forms are also lost into oblivion. We do not know the material or the knowledge which a palm-leaf contains in it as there is no documentation, publication, editing etc. done by the custodians.

As discussed above, ours have 90% of the manuscripts which are in these un-organized sectors. Only 10% of the manuscripts in Oḍiṣā are collected and preserved in Museums and Archives. So to save our documentary and literary heritage posterity which is abundant with themes like Purāṇic literature, Āyurvedic texts, tantric cults, mystic traditions, astronomy, astrology, customary social beliefs, different ways of worships, methods of social practices etc.- these are to be preserved through various means, say, conservation, digitization, and dissemination to the public.

Conclusion - Though digitization makes the content of the manuscripts public for research and other purposes, still it has its own drawbacks and may be obsolete in a fast in properly seasoned palm-leaf and disseminate to the youths, scholars, students, moving technological era. So along with digitization we should copy the manuscripts public through academic institutions like schools, colleges, universities, libraries, museums, archives, and other public or private institutions so that our posterior generation should know the content and context of the palm-leaf manuscript heritage of Oḍiṣā which has its own glorious phase in Indian ancient manuscript traditions as is evident from the data available from the National Mission for Manuscripts which as umbrella organization has done a splendid job in not only Oḍiṣā but all over India as well as abroad in surveying, digitizing and conserving this great intellectual wealth of a nation like India. The copying method of manuscripts in present age is to be inspired as writing tradition on palm-leaf is more than a thousand of years of legacy of human civilization and also a dying art form which needs technical expertise by an artisan, hence to be energized for the growth of a new discipline of study and techniques.

In Oḍiṣā, we should reap the benefits out of the provisions of National Mission for Manuscripts in a big way, especially for the un-organized repositories in the private or non-government sector where-in there is ignorance, poverty, lack of will power and technical expertise. Once these are lost, it is a permanent loss for the nation and most of them have not only permanently lost but this unfortunate thing is still going on and we should be prompt enough to revive and restore these manuscripts in Tungis or Gādi Gharas and private house-holds which are unfortunately being allowed to deteriorate in the name of worship and ritual practices. So, the need of the hour and our focus should be more upon these un-organized sectors which are more prone to destruction compared to Government Museums/ Archives which are having its own mechanism of funds, technical personnel, infrastructure, and exposure to the intellectual world. These Bhāgavatatuṅḡīs or Gādigharas, fortunately, are now being revived by the Government of Oḍiṣā, of late. And we should welcome this noble and humble step and intellectual world should cooperate in this great endeavour to preserve, promote and protect for posterity.

Photo Gallery:

(Indigenous /Traditional
Methods of Preservations)
(Modern Methods of
Preservations)

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